

Supplementary Figure S1. Secondary structure of the 22 tRNAs of *Glaniaetania osculata* (PX326266; IPCAS-CZ17). All other proteocephalids depict the same pattern. Note the lack of the DHU-arm in the MT-TR and MT-S1 genes.

Alanine MT-TA (TGC)

Cysteine MT-TC (GCA)

Aspartate MT-TD (GTC)

Glutamate MT-TE (TTC)

Phenylalanine MT-TF (GAA)

Glycine MT-TG (TCC)

Histidine MT-TH (GTG)

Isoleucine MT-TI (GAT)

Lysine MT-TK (CTT)

Leucine MT-TL1 (TAG)

Leucine MT-TL2 (TAA)

Methionine MT-TM (CAT)

Asparagine MT-TN (GTT)

Proline MT-TP (TGG)

Glutamine MT-TQ (TTG)

Arginine MT-TR (ACG)

Serine MT-TS1 (GCT)

Serine MT-TS2 (TGA)

Threonine MT-TT (TGT)

Valine MT-TV (TAC)

Tryptophan MT-TW (TCA)

Tyrosine MT-TY (GTA)

